

Juridical Study on Interfaith Marriage Practices in Sleman Regency

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Abstract

The issue of interfaith marriage is a polemic that has been discussed until now. The problem is, with interfaith marriages, there will be a principles difference in the marriage, so it is feared that it will cause various complicated issues to be resolved in the future. On the one hand, there is still a debate on the legal basis for declaring the validity and invalidity of the marriage. The title is a Juridical Study on the Legality of Interfaith Marriages in the Perspective of Law no. 16 of 2019. In Sleman Regency, the formulation of the problem is what are the factors behind interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency and how is the Mechanism of Interfaith Marriage in Sleman Regency. This study aims to find out and analyze the factors behind interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency and to find out and analyze the legitimacy of interfaith marriages based on Law Number 16 of 2019 concerning Marriage. Legal research method with the type of field research with a normative-empirical approach that uses secondary and primary data. The results obtained by the author are the factors behind interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency. First, the religious understanding of each party is strong. Second is the agreement between the prospective husband and wife to carry out interfaith marriages. Third, do not want to give up his belief. Fourth is the contraction process from the extended family to the parent family. and Fifth, Changes in principles in marriage institutions the mechanism for interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency which applies for a court order at the Sleman District Court for interfaith marriages, then the determination is submitted to the Population and Civil Registry Office of Sleman Regency for administrative records of interfaith marriages

Keywords: *Marriage, Different Religion, Sleman Regency.*

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is a human instinct since the existence of humans themselves to fulfill their life needs in carrying out biological relationships in a family. Of course, marriage involves at least a relationship between two parties, which in legal terms is called a legal relationship, where each party has rights and obligations. There is an objective law that regulates it called marriage law. Therefore, for religious adherents, marriage engagement is not considered an ordinary engagement but is sacred and contains religious teachings for its followers. Of course, they cannot escape the objective legal provisions regulated in their respective religions and specific state laws.

In the diverse conditions of Indonesian society, in terms of ethnicity, religion, and race, various problems arise, such as problems in the distribution of inheritance in the family and the issue of what kind of custom applies in a family rule. One of the problems in the spotlight in the conflicts that arise in today's society is where we often encounter interfaith wedding parties.

In the Republic of Indonesia, as a country based on Pancasila, where the first precept is the Belief in One God. So marriage is considered to have a very close relationship with religion, so marriage does not only contain physical/physical elements. But the mental/spiritual part also has an important role, especially since the enactment of Marriage Law No. 1 of 1974, which has been national since January 2, 1974, where in article 2 paragraph 1, it is stated that there is no marriage outside the law of each religion and belief. In this way, our positive law further confirms the role of religion and belief. With Article 2 paragraph 1 of the Marriage Law No. 16 of 2019, implementation according to each religion and belief has become an absolute requirement to determine whether a marriage is legal. There is no problem if marriage is only between people of the same religion or faith (Ruslie, 2012).

If we look at Marriage Law No. 1 of 1974 and the implementing regulations of P.P. no. 9 of 1975, the two rules do not explicitly regulate the issue of interfaith marriage. If we examine these two regulations, we can only conclude that there is no single article, either expressly or impliedly, that prohibits interfaith marriages.¹ The issue of interfaith marriage is a polemic that has been discussed until now. The problem is, with interfaith marriages, there will be a principle difference in the marriage, so it is feared that it will cause various complicated issues to be resolved in the future. On the one hand, there is still a debate on the legal basis for declaring the validity and invalidity of the marriage. Therefore, it becomes interesting to discuss the issue of marriage between followers of different religions, both in terms of Islamic law and positive law that applies in Indonesia. In Islam, interfaith marriage or interfaith marriage is a long-standing problem, but it

is always hot to talk about until now. In reality, interfaith marriages still occur in society, and here there are differences of opinion among scholars regarding the issue of halal and haram marriages. Most scholars from ancient times until now have agreed that it is forbidden for a Muslim woman to marry a non-Muslim man and vice versa. A man is prohibited from marrying a non-Muslim woman, based on the verse of the Koran surah al-Baqarah (2) verse 221. From this verse, it can be understood that Allah forbids marriage between Muslim men and non-Muslim women and vice versa; Muslim women are prohibited from marrying non-Muslim men.

The basis of religious law in marriage is fundamental in Law no. 16 of 2019, so the determination of whether or not marriage is permissible depends on religious provisions. This also means that religious law states that marriage is not allowed, which is also not acceptable according to state law. So in a marriage of different religions, whether it is permissible depends on the religion's provisions.

In the view of fiqh, the ideal marriage is a marriage carried out by a balanced male and female partner to create a *sakinah, mawaddah warahmah* family. Such a family will be enveloped in the sense of peace, full of love and affection. Such marriage will only happen if the husband and wife adhere to the same religion. However, if they marry a couple of different faiths, and the marriage is maintained, it will cause many problems in the family because the two religions are different, such as in the implementation of worship, choosing children's education, fostering children's careers, choosing food menus and other problems.

The marriage law in Indonesia does not explicitly regulate the marriage of interfaith couples, so there is a legal vacuum. Regarding the validity of marriage, marriage is carried out according to religion and belief as regulated in Article 2 paragraph (1) of the UUP. This means that the Marriage Law submits to the teachings of each faith.

In practice, interfaith marriages can occur in Indonesia. Professor of Civil Law at the University of Indonesia, Prof. Wahyono Darmabrata, explained that there are four popular ways that interfaith couples take so that their marriage can take place. According to Wahyono, the four ways are:

1. Request a court order
2. Marriage is carried out according to each religion
3. Temporary submission to one of the religious laws
4. Married abroad.

There is a Supreme Court (M.A.) jurisprudence, namely the Supreme Court Decision No.1400 K/Pdt/1986. The Supreme Court's decision stated, among other things, that the Civil Registry Office was allowed to hold interfaith marriages at that time. In its decision, the Supreme Court noted that by submitting a marriage registration at the Civil Registry Office, a person (ISLAM) has chosen not to have his marriage held according to the Islamic religion. Thus, choosing to follow a non-Islamic religion, the Civil Registry Office must carry out and register the marriage. In this case, based on the Supreme Court's decision, if you wish to report your marriage at the Civil Registry Office, you can look for religious leaders who have different perceptions and are willing to marry off their partners according to their perceptions of religious teachings. Then, if the Civil Registry Office grants the application for marriage registration, the marriage is legal according to law.

Based on the description of the formulation of the problem, the objectives of this research are as follows:

1. To find out and analyze the factors behind interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency.
2. To find out the practice of interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Legal Basis of Marriage

Like other worship, marriage has a legal basis that makes it advisable to be done by Muslims. According to Muhammad (2008), the legal basis for marriage based on the Qur'an and Hadith is as follows:

"O humanity! Be mindful of your Lord Who created you from a single soul, and from it He created its mate, and through both He spread countless men and women. And be mindful of Allah—in Whose Name you appeal to one another—and 'honour' family ties. Surely Allah is ever Watchful over you". (Q.S. An-Nisaa: 1).

"Marry off the 'free' singles among you, as well as the righteous of your bondmen and bondwomen. If they are poor, Allah will enrich them out of His bounty. For Allah is All-Bountiful, All-Knowing." (Q.S. An-Nuur: 32)

"And one of His signs is that He created for you spouses from among yourselves so that you may find comfort in them. And He has placed between you compassion and mercy. Surely in this are signs for people who reflect." (Q.S. Ar-Ruum:21).

"O youths, whoever among you has the ability to marry, let him marry; because getting married lowers the gaze and guards the genitals more. As for whoever is not able to get married, let him fast; because fasting is a silencer (desire)". (Narrated by al-Bukhari from 'Abdullah bin Mas'ud Radhiyallahu anhu).

Interfaith Marriage

Interfaith marriages (mixed marriages) are marriages between a man and woman subject to different laws because of different religions. Interfaith marriages between Indonesian citizens, namely Indonesian men and Indonesian women have different faiths/beliefs.

Professor of Civil Law at the University of Indonesia, Prof. Wahyono Darmabrata, explained that there are four popular ways that interfaith couples take so that their marriage can take place. According to Wahyono, the four ways are:

1. Request a court order,
2. Marriage is carried out according to each religion,
3. Temporary submission to one of the religious laws, and
4. Married abroad.

The marriage law in Indonesia does not explicitly regulate the marriage of interfaith couples, so there is a legal vacuum. Regarding the validity of marriage, marriage is carried out according to religion and belief as regulated in Article 2 paragraph (1) of the UUP. This means that the Marriage Law submits to the teachings of each faith. However, the problem is whether the religion adopted by each party allows for interfaith marriages to be carried out. For example, in Islam, women are not allowed to marry men who are not Muslim (Al Baqarah [2]: 221). In addition, in Christian teachings, marriage is prohibited (II Corinthians 6:14-18).

METHOD

In the case of interfaith marriage, the research approach uses a normative-empirical legal approach that uses secondary and primary data. This normative-empirical approach combines a normative legal course with the addition of various empirical elements. The normative-empirical legal research method regarding the implementation of normative legal provisions (laws) in their actions in every particular legal event in a society (Muhammad, 2008). Normative Legal Research is legal research conducted by examining library materials or secondary data (Muhammad, 2008). According to Ronny Soemitro (2010), empirical legal research is legal research with primary data or data obtained directly from the source. In empirical research, the thing studied is primarily preliminary data.

The data collection method in this research is a literature study, namely by reviewing various laws and regulations or literature related to research problems, then analyzing and drawing conclusions. Then another data collection technique is needed in the form of documentation to test, interpret, and interpret the existing issues by tracing and studying documents in the form of files on the determination of interfaith marriages at the Sleman Civil Registry Office and the Sleman District Court and digging up data that can support this discussion from the literature law as well as the interview method is used to obtain various information by meeting face to face with resource persons to exchange information and ideas through question and answer. By involving two parties, namely interviewers and informants, in this study, the author uses an open interview method for parties who can provide accurate information on this research.

The data obtained from library research and field research were then analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods, namely by analyzing data obtained through field research and library research after being selected based on problems. Then it is arranged systematically and seen for its conformity with the applicable provisions, then concluded so that the answers to the problems are obtained.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Factors Behind Interfaith Marriages in Sleman Regency

Factors behind interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency based on a resource person named Mr. H. Mohamad Sholeh, SH., MH. as a Judge at the Sleman District Court who explained that:

1. The religious understanding of each party is strong;
2. An agreement between the prospective husband and wife to carry out interfaith marriages; and

3. Don't want to give up their beliefs.

Based on the results of interviews with resource persons named Mr. Drs. Susmiarto, MM, the Head of the Population and Civil Registration Office of Sleman Regency, explained that religion generally does not allow its people to marry people of different faiths. Especially in Sleman Regency, there are still many interfaith marriages. This happens because of 2 (two) factors, namely the contraction process from the extended family to the parent family and changes in principles in the marriage system.

1. The occurrence of a contraction process from the extended family to the parent family
Changes in family structure that occur in society also happen in families of different religions. The change in structure is in the form of a family contraction process which is the process of changing from an extended family to a parent family. This process of family contraction gave rise to a stronger nuclear family's authority and liberalization. The existence of the authority to direct the level of independence of the nuclear family is high. This autonomy was accompanied by the deregulation of the nuclear family (members). Nuclear family members have more freedom in deciding all matters relating to internal family matters.

In this regard, the nuclear family that is related or members of the breed still communicate with each other, but that does not mean that the nuclear family that is related has influence or intervenes in parent family matters unless specifically requested to determine a mating partner. The intervention of parents or other parent families in parent family matters is acceptable as long as it is to solve the problem, but it is not wise if it is not asked for. Actions such as "bener nanging ora pener". This means that getting involved in parent family problems, for example, by giving advice, is good and right, but it is not wise if there is no request from the person concerned.

The substantial authority will lead to the liberalization of the parent family due to the family contraction process, which is the cause of interfaith marriages. The reasons for these factors indicate weakened social control from extended relatives over the parent family (members). This, in the end, gives freedom for the parent family to determine marriage partners without considering the values that become the reference for broad relatives, especially religious values.

2. Changes in principles in marriage institutions.

Changes in Javanese culture related to marriage arrangements, for example, the principle of *gudel nyusu kebo* (children follow the wishes of parents), which turned into *kebo nyusu gudel* (parents follow the wishes of children). This principle explains children's independence and freedom in determining their mate. The term *kebo nyusu gudel* is somewhat different from *tut wuri handayani*. The term *tut wuri handayani* is submission to the person who runs it, and that person (parents) encourages to carry it out. While in terms of *kebo nyusu gudel*, parents only follow the child's wishes without encouraging the child to carry them out. In this regard, parents may accept forcefully, even if they do not agree in their hearts.

Most parents' differences in area, ethnicity, level of education, occupation, and race are not the main problems in determining a marriage partner. As mentioned in the first factor, parents do not have a problem with religious differences. The most crucial factor is consensual (*tresno*) between potential partners.

Based on the description that has been submitted, the authors argue that the factors behind interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency are:

1. The religious understanding of each party is strong.
2. An agreement between a prospective husband and wife to carry out interfaith marriages.
3. Don't want to give up their beliefs.
4. The occurrence of a contraction process from the extended family to the parent family.
5. Changes in principles in marriage institutions.

Interfaith Marriage Practices in Sleman Regency

In this case, because you are a Muslim male, and in Islam, it is still allowed to marry of different religions if the male is Muslim and the female is of another faith. However, in the Catholic teaching adopted by the couple, interfaith marriages are prohibited.

Indonesian positive law relates to national marriage law as defined in Article 2 paragraph (1) of the marriage law, which has the meaning that Indonesian marriages that have occurred in Indonesia can only be held when the couple is a couple who share the same religion even though they are a different race, ethnicity or nation. The meaning of mixed marriage as regulated in Articles 57 to 62 of the Marriage Law has emphasized that what is meant by mixed marriages are marriages that occur due to differences in citizenship. Thus, the Marriage Law has clarified the invalidity of diverse marriages due to religious differences for those who wish to hold their marriages in Indonesia.

In the life of a pluralistic Indonesian society, religious criteria are sometimes neglected and not prioritized, so it is not uncommon to meet married couples with different beliefs (religions). If studied more deeply, marriage is the unification of two people who are different from one another to get together, but not in terms of other religions. The definition of

marriage, as affirmed in Article 1 of the Law on Marriage, has stated that the purpose of marriage is to form a happy and eternal family based on the One Supreme Godhead.

Referring to the fatwa of the Indonesian Ulema Council based on the National Deliberation (Munas) II on 11-17 Rajab 1400H, coinciding with 26 May-1 June 1980 A.D., the MUI issued a fatwa that interfaith marriages or mixed marriages are haraam.

According to Karsayua (2016), the consequences of interfaith marriages are as follows:

1. Regarding the validity of the marriage, which will give rise to rights and obligations between husband and wife (wife's rights to livelihood and joint property);
2. The status of the child born, the child born from an illegitimate marriage only has a civil legal relationship with his mother;
3. Inheritance rights (because religious differences invalidate the right to inherit from each other);
4. The problem of the court was where to settle household disputes (Judicial institutions in Indonesia recognize absolute and relative authority and the principle of personality).

In Indonesia, it can be said that interfaith marriages are not regulated in the national Marriage Law because religious teachings do not justify interfaith marriages. There are obstacles to marriage if the marriage continues because it is not following what is desired by Article 2 Paragraph (1) and Article 8 letter f of the Marriage Law. Article 2 Paragraph (1) of the Marriage Law contains marriage is legal if it is carried out according to the laws of each religion and belief. Based on the description above, the writer argues that the primary requirement in the validity of marriage still refers to the rules and regulations of their respective religions.

The Supreme Court issued the jurisprudence of Supreme Court Decision No.1400K/PDT/1986, which stated that interfaith marriages were legal in Indonesia in line with the court's decision. Based on the information from the informant, the court's decision will later be used as the basis for the registration of interfaith marriages at the Population and Civil Registration Service.

Based on Article 35 Letter (a) of Law Number 23 of 2006 concerning Population Administration, interfaith couples can be able to register their marriage as long as they obtain a prior determination from the District Court. Referring to the explanation of Article 35 of Law Number 23 of 2006 concerning Population Administration, namely "Marriage determined by the Court" is a marriage performed between people of different religions.

According to Mr. Drs. Susmiarto, MM, the Head of the Population and Civil Registration Office of Sleman Regency, explained that the Disdukcapil only has an administrative function so that marriages of different religions have legal force in Indonesia without considering the material requirements of marriage. The prospective partner must carry out the procedure to notify the Disdukcapil where the prospective spouse is domiciled about the implementation of the marriage. In the case of applying for interfaith marriage, it is obligatory to apply for interfaith marriage to the District Court according to the domicile of the prospective bride and groom. Then when a decision has been issued from the local District Court, the determination is used as the basis for the Sleman Disdukcapil recording of the marriage.

In Article 3 of Government Regulation no. 9 of 1975, it is stated that every person who wishes to enter into a marriage must notify the intention, either orally or in writing, to the registrar at the place where the marriage will take place, at least 10 (ten) working days before the marriage takes place. At the same time, the provisions beyond the 10 working days may ask for permission from the sub-district head on behalf of the regent if there are reasons that are deemed essential.

According to Article 6 of Government Regulation no. 9 of 1975, the registrar, in addition to examining whether the conditions for marriage have been met and whether there are no obstacles to marriage according to the law, must also examine:

1. Quotation of the prospective bride's birth certificate;
2. Information regarding the name, religion/belief, occupation, and place of residence of the parents of the prospective bride and groom;
3. Written permission/court permit as referred to in Article 6 paragraph (2), (3), (4), (5) Law no. 1 of 1974;
4. Court/official permission as referred to in Article 4 of Law no. 1 of 1974 concerning marriage;
5. Court/official dispensation as referred to in Article 7 paragraph (2) of Law no. 1 of 1974 concerning marriage;
6. Wife/husband's death certificate or divorce certificate for marriage for the second or more time;
7. Written permission from the official appointed by the MENHANKAM PANGAB if one of the prospective bride and groom or both are members of the Armed Forces;
8. The registrar ratifies authentic or underhand power of attorney if one of the prospective brides or both cannot attend alone for an important reason so that they represent others (Summa, 2004).

After the fulfillment of the procedures and requirements for notification, and there are no obstacles to the marriage, the registrar will announce the announcement of the intention to carry out the marriage at the marriage registration office at a place that has been determined and is easy to read by the public.

Article 9 further stipulates matters that must be included in the announcement. Then, Article 10 and Article 11 regulate the marriage procedure. According to Article 10 of Government Regulation no. 9 of 1975, a marriage may occur after the tenth day since the announcement per the marriage procedure according to the law of each religion and belief, before the Registrar's Office in the presence of 2 (two) witnesses. Shortly after the marriage, the bride and groom sign the marriage certificate, followed by the two witnesses and the registrar, and by the marriage guardian or his representative for marriages carried out according to the Islamic religion. By signing the marriage certificate, the marriage has been officially registered.

In practice, Government Regulation no. 9 of 1975 has not entirely and wholly regulated the implementation of the provisions contained in Law no. 1 of 1974. Based on this, civil servants can make policies by not only enforcing the conditions of Law no. 1 of 1974 concerning existing marriages and complete implementing regulations.

Therefore, to maintain a legal vacuum, it is not only to enforce the old regulations as long as they are not regulated in Law no. 1 of 1974 concerning marriage, but it is also appropriate to apply the old regulations which, although already regulated in Law no. 1 of 1974 but the implementing regulations do not exist or are incomplete as in the implementation of marriage. This means that marriages only carried out in the Civil Registry are also considered valid. Thus, whether the performance of the marriage does not conflict with Article 2 paragraph (1) of Law no. 1 of 1974 jo. Article 10 paragraphs (2) and (3) of P.P. No. 9 of 1975, we believe that until now, there has never been a court decision that annuls or declares that marriages held in the Civil Registry are invalid.

The implementation of interfaith marriages, following the conditions specified in Article 6 paragraph (1) Government Regulation no. 9 of 1975, then what usually becomes a problem is to get a "Religious Certificate" for people who want to carry out interfaith marriages that are prohibited by their religion. For Muslim women who want to marry men who are not Muslim, in practice, they have never received a certificate or dispensation from the Marriage Registrar at the Ministry of Religion office. For a Muslim man, whether or not he can obtain a religious certificate depends on the opinion/view of the authorized Marriage Registrar regarding whether it is permissible or not for a Muslim man to marry a non-Muslim woman. If the Marriage Registrar refuses, the only way for the Muslim man is to use the rejection letter as a basis for filing an objection to the Religious Court.

People who are Catholic will be able to get a Certificate of Religion if they promise to remain faithful to their beliefs and are willing to educate their children in a Catholic way. There is no problem for those who are Protestant because the Protestant church does not forbid its people from interfaith marriages. For those who are Hindus and Buddhists, even though their religion forbids interfaith marriages, in practice, it is not too difficult to obtain a Religious Certificate. The Hindu Religion will provide the required certificate if the prospective bride and groom promise to be faithful to each other, and "Hinduism forbids inter-religious marriages only if the marriage wants to be carried out according to Hinduism. Hinduism will not prevent its followers from marrying according to other religions or at the Civil Registry Office" (Summa, 2004).

Although positive law and Islamic law in Indonesia do not provide space for interfaith marriages, several couples continue to hold interfaith marriages under the pretext of love or human rights. Professor of Civil Law at the University of Indonesia, Prof. Wahyono Darmabrata, explained that there are four popular ways that interfaith couples take so that their marriage can take place. The four ways are:

1. Request a court order
2. Marriage is carried out according to each religion
3. Temporary submission to one of the religious laws
4. Married abroad.

Based on the interview results with Mr. Wisnu, the practice of interfaith marriage is administratively the same as marriage in general. There are no special requirements, so the marriage can be carried out according to their respective religions.

According to Mr. WS, the marriage takes place in the church or the bride first because both the bride and groom are committed to their respective religions. At KUA, they must say the shahada while the bride and groom have had a previous commitment. This is to find a middle way to carry out their marriage.

In practice, marriages held at the Pugeran Church were shortened. This is because the head of the family adheres to the Islamic religion, so the rules that should run according to the Catholic faith are condensed only at the core of the marriage.

Mr. WS said that in the sacrament or blessing of Islamic marriage, there is no problem in the wedding procession because each bride and groom commit to their respective beliefs.

If a person has become a Muslim, then his children must follow his father's religion. However, because this couple applies the principle of religious freedom to their children and to make it easier for them to choose the religion they believe in in the future, they decided to marry in Islam, but their marital status is different administratively.

On April 19, 2020, the interfaith marriage between W.S. (Islam) and S.T. (Catholic), which was held at the Pugeran Church, began with the blessing and confirmation of marriage by the Pastor. Starting with First, Preparation singing together "Love from Heaven" by the spouse and the congregation in attendance. This is followed by invitation to worship by the priest to ask for blessings for the bride and groom. Then, the Pastor read the advisory NATS, said a prayer, and conveyed the word, followed by reciting the marriage vows and exchanging rings. After that, the Pastor performed the blessing and confirmation of the marriage and closed by singing the congregation's praise of "Love" and voluntary giving to celebrate the wedding event. Finally, the sending and blessing by the Pastor and approved by the community.

After the blessing procession, according to Catholicism, is complete, the marriage procession is continued in an Islamic way, namely the marriage contract, which begins with the opening, giving thanks, and reading al-Fatihah, followed by the marriage sermon. Then the wedding officiant ensures that the pillars of marriage have been fulfilled by the prospective bride, guardian, and witness. The guardian in this marriage is the brother of the prospective bride. However, if the guardian of the prospective bride cannot do so, then the wedding officiant can also act as guardian of the judge. The next event was reading the qabul consent between the guardian and the groom, followed by the reading of prayers, signing the marriage certificate, and handing over the dowry.

After the religious procession is carried out, and the marriage is considered valid by the respective religion of the bride and groom, it will be reported to the civil registry with a marriage ratification letter from the church or religious leader containing information that Catholicism or another religion has blessed the couple. However, if the Civil Registry Office refuses because it knows that the couple's identity is of a different faith, they are forced to deal with it administratively. One of the parties takes care of a baptismal certificate or certificate of conversion to another religion or, in other words, makes temporary legal compliance.

CONCLUSION

The factors behind interfaith marriages in Sleman Regency are a solid religious understanding of each party, an agreement between prospective husband and wife to carry out interfaith marriages, not wanting to give up their beliefs, the occurrence of a contraction process from the extended family to the parent family, and changes in principles-principles in marriage institutions. Based on the practice of interfaith marriages in Indonesia, they cannot obtain legality (legitimacy) because the provisions of Indonesian marriages can only be carried out when the couple is a partner of the same religion. However, when interfaith marriages are carried out abroad, or one of the parties submits to one of their religions, the interfaith marriage is legally valid.

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